

Church of Almighty God (Quannengshen jiaohui 全能神教會) / Eastern Lightning (Dongfang shandian 東方閃電)

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The “Church of Almighty God” (Quannengshen jiaohui 全能神教會), also known as “Eastern Lightning” (Dongfang shandian 東方閃電), is a Protestant-inspired religious organization in post-Mao China and among Chinese diasporas worldwide. Its popular nickname, “Eastern Lightning,” derives from Matthews 24:27, which prophesizes the future advent of God: “For as lightning that comes from the east is visible even in the west, so will be the coming of the Son of Man.” In line with earlier Chinese Christian communities, the Church of Almighty God (CAG) understands this iconic quotation as referring to the second advent of Christ as taking place in China. According to its teachings, Christ has already revealed himself, incarnated as a woman from central China. More importantly, practitioners believe that the Second Christ has revealed a new set of scriptures that supersede the conventional teachings, values, and practices codified in the Bible. Resembling traditional Chinese sectarian concepts of three stages in cosmic history (such as in Xiantiandao and Yiguandao), the Second Christ’s activities mark the third period in God’s scheme, which is the “Age of the Kingdom” (guodu shidai 國度時代). The CAG emerged in the milieu of Protestant-inspired new religious groups and underground churches in post-Mao China, a time marked by the rise of the Qigong wave and the emergence of Falungong 法輪功. Departing from conventional Protestantism, many Protestant-inspired groups sought to adapt Christian teachings to Chinese contexts by adding other symbols, teachings, and practices. For instance, many cherish steadfast faith as the central pillar of individual practice and well-being, and they promote an apocalyptic and millenarian understanding of the Christian tradition. Despite the abundance of material related to matters of faith provided online by the CAG, little is known of daily religious life in its communities. From what we know, the church promotes an iconoclastic framework that applies to standard Christian rituals and festivals (such as Christmas, Easter, or communion) and Chinese traditional festivals and cultural practices. Meetings do not seem to follow a formal liturgy for worship. Rather, members listen to sermons and share their thoughts and experiences afterward. Accordingly, writing and publishing testimonies, primarily through CAG websites, is among the most cherished practices of pious adepts. Most of them relate to spiritual journeys and how steadfast faith in the powers of Almighty God was instrumental in overcoming hardships. Even though the names of the founder and other leaders are almost absent from CAG material, it seems that it was founded by Zhao Weishan 趙維山 (b. 1951), a man from the northeastern Chinese province of Heilongjiang 黑龍江省. Before founding CAG in Henan Province 河南省, central China, in ca. 1991, he was affiliated with various Protestant-inspired groups in the late 1980s. It was he who declared a woman as the second incarnation of Christ. Usually, her name is absent from CAG material as well. In 2012, Chinese authorities revealed her purported identity as Yang Xiangbin 楊向彬 (b. 1973) from Shanxi Province 山西省 (just north of Henan), but this claim has not been corroborated by the CAG and academic scholars. Interpreted as the “utterances of Christ of the last days,” the Second Christ’s speeches were collected and evolved into the group’s focal scripture Hua zai roushen xianxian 話在肉身顯現 (The Word Appears in the Flesh). At the moment, it consists of two volumes: the first comprises texts from 1991 to 1997; the second was published in 2014 and has since outranked the first as the more authoritative scripture. Remarkably, in this volume and other recent publications, the role of the female Christ seems to have shrunk compared to that of Almighty God. Like many other Protestant-inspired

groups, the CAG was declared an “evil cult” (xiejiao 邪教) in 1995. Even though robust statistics are not available and CAG activists sometimes report contradictory figures, several crackdowns by the Chinese government seem to have resulted in the detainment of up to hundreds of thousands of people. Moreover, according to CAG activists, at least dozens of practitioners have been killed by the authorities or died during detention. According to ethnographic research and unconfirmed claims, Zhao and the female Christ escaped to the United States in the early 2000s. During the 1990s and 2000s, the CAG seems to have been strongest in Henan and neighboring provinces, many of which are considered rural and poor compared to the fancy global metropolises of Shanghai, Beijing, and Shenzhen. Initially, most practitioners appeared to be elderly and often illiterate women, but more recent research indicates that the CAG also thrives in metropolitan areas. In 2014, the Chinese authorities estimated there would be 4 million practitioners in China, but these high numbers are likely exaggerated by public security institutions to justify the harsh measures. Due to the ongoing suppression of the church, during the past decade, considerable communities have also been established by refugees in South Korea, the Philippines, and the United States. The church is well-known for its opposition to conventional Christians unwilling to accept the superiority of their new revelations, for which they are labeled as “fake” or “anti-Christ” (jiajidu / dijidu 假基督/ 敵基督). Similarly, practitioners conceive of the Chinese Communist Party (CCP) as the “great red dragon” (dahonglong 大紅龍) mentioned in Revelation 12, i.e., an incarnation of Satan. Accordingly, the church’s confrontation with the Party attains an eschatological meaning. Probably for these reasons, the CAG is a highly controversial organization in China and beyond. Chinese Christians and the government have blamed it for its allegedly coercive proselytization strategies, kidnapping, maltreatment, violence, and even involvement in a highly publicized homicide. On May 28, 2014, a group of six who allegedly belonged to the church killed a saleswoman in a McDonald’s restaurant in eastern China’s Zhaoyuan City 招遠市 (Shandong Province 山東省). The authorities were quick to blame the crime on the CAG, but close scrutiny by Western scholars suggests that the group was not a part of the church anymore or never has been. Still, the McDonald’s murder incident has firmly established the church’s negative image in the Chinese public, but also in Western media. Like in the case of Falungong, the Internet plays a pivotal role in the CAG’s activities: to circulate the scriptures and messages and to sustain a globally dispersed community. Besides archiving free books and other readings, especially testimonies, CAG websites provide many other services in different languages (41, at the moment of writing), including music videos, movies, sermons, hotlines, and a mobile phone app. In addition, the church also operates YouTube, Facebook, and Instagram accounts.

Date Range: 1991 CE - 2024 CE

Region: The Church of Almighty God's early stronghold (1990s and 2000s)

Region tags: Asia, Shanxi, Anhui, East Asia, China, Shandong, Henan Province, Jiangsu Province

The Church of Almighty God was founded in 1991 in Henan Province 河南省, central China. During its early phase, it was strongest in Henan and its neighboring provinces, especially Anhui 安徽省 and Shandong 山東省.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Dunn, Emily. *Lightning from the East: Heterodoxy and Christianity in Contemporary China. Religion in Chinese societies 8.* Leiden: Brill, 2015.

- Source 2: Introvigne, Massimo. *Inside the Church of Almighty God: The Most Persecuted Religious Movement in China*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2020.
- Source 3: Pan, Junliang. "Messianism and Politics in Contemporary China: The Church of Almighty God." *Review of Religion and Chinese Society* 2, no. 2 (2015): 186–215. <https://doi.org/10.1163/22143955-00202003>.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.holyspiritspeaks.org/>
- Source 1 Description: Official English website

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://en.godfootsteps.org/>
- Source 1 Description: Official English website of the Church of Almighty God, available in 41 languages; provides many different materials, including free books and practitioners' testimonies
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.hidden-advent.org/>
- Source 2 Description: the Chinese version of the church's website in simplified characters uses a different URL, but the content seems to be similar
- Source 3 URL: <https://news.sina.com.cn/c/2014-08-22/123730728266.shtml>
- Source 3 Description: "Shandong Zhaoyuan xue'an beigao zibai: wo jiu shi shen 山東招遠血案被告自白:我就是神," the original Chinese text of the main culprits' depositions during the 2014 McDonald's murder trial

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: There seems to be high competition between CAG and other Protestant communities. Those Christian groups that do not accept the superiority of their new revelations are sometimes labeled "fake" or "anti-Christ" (jiajidu / dijidu 假基督 / 敵基督). In addition, the CAG also rejects traditional Chinese beliefs and practices, including Confucianism, Daoism, and praying to deities.

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: Generally speaking, interaction with out-group people does not seem to involve violence. However, some Chinese Christian communities and the government blame CAG for its use of coercion, maltreatment, and violence regarding proselytization. Western scholars, especially the sociologist Massimo Introvigne, vividly deny these claims, but more research is needed in this regard.

Reference: Introvigne, Massimo. "Captivity Narratives: Did the Church of Almighty God Kidnap 34 Evangelical Pastors in 2002?". *The Journal of CESNUR* 2, no. 1 (2018): 100-110.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Because ethnographic fieldwork is impossible in China for political reasons, only little is known about the daily religious life.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Notes: While this seems to be the case, generally speaking, some Chinese Christians and government agencies have accused the CAG of using coercive means and psychological

violence for proselytization. The accuracy of these accounts, however, is strongly contested.

Reference: Introvigne, Massimo. *Inside the Church of Almighty God: The Most Persecuted Religious Movement in China*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2020.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Labeled as a "heterodox sect" (xiejiao 邪教), the CAG has been banned in the People's Republic of China since 1995. It has been subject to various crackdowns and media campaigns.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Because ethnographic fieldwork is impossible in China for political reasons, only little is known about the daily religious life.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No statistics are available, mainly because ethnographic fieldwork in the People's Republic is impossible, and the church does not provide accurate figures. In 2014, the Chinese authorities estimated there would be 4 million practitioners in China, but these high numbers are likely exaggerated by public security institutions to justify the harsh measures.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (intolerant of other affiliations)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Again, because of the limited amount of data available, little is known regarding the organization of the church.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: The primary scripture is Hua zai roushen xianxian 話在肉身顯現 (The Word Appears in the Flesh), which was published in two volumes in 1997 and 2014. It consists of speeches delivered by the Second Christ in the 1990s and 2000s.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: They are revealed by the Second Christ, who incarnated herself as a woman. In more recent publications, however, the CAG seems to have altered the narrative and replaced the female Christ with a male one. Because of the limited ethnographic data available, scholars so far are not able to provide a persuasive interpretation for this shift.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: It is not formally codified, but the CAG websites provide a clearly defined collection of scriptures.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: Because the CAG has been banned in China since 1995 and has been subject to persecution many times, practitioners likely meet in private residences or existing churches, similar to the Chinese "house church movement."

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

Notes: Heaven does not play a pivotal role in the CAG's publications.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

Notes: Hell also does not play a central role in the church's writings.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: the Millennial Kingdom

Notes: The main point of interest in CAG writings is how Almighty God will bring about the "Millennial Kingdom" (Qiannian guodu 千年國度) on earth, as prophesied in Revelation.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Following standard Christian parlance, CAG scriptures discern a supreme and uncontested extramundane creator, which they term Almighty God (Quannengshen 全能神), and his entourage of angels. They represent the ultimate truth that will help practitioners attain salvation. By contrast, evil spirits and demons work on behalf of Satan to counteract Almighty God's divine plan. According to the church's eschatology, however, their attempts are to no avail, as, ultimately, Almighty God will establish the third and final cosmic period of the "Millennial Kingdom" (qiannian guodu 千年國度), during which Satan and his allies are bound and the Second Christ reigns the world. Altogether, angels do not seem to play a pivotal role in the church's eschatological narrative, but Almighty God is the sole center of attention regarding beliefs and practices.

A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No
 - Notes: CAG writings exhibit a strong iconoclastic attitude and explicitly inhibit practitioners from worshipping other deities and reading texts of different religions.
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The woman who appears to have delivered the speeches that are the foundation of the CAG's focal scripture, Hua zai roushen xianxian 話在肉身顯現 (The Word Appears in the Flesh), is recognized by coreligionists as the Second Christ.
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - No

- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - No
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside

of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - I don't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - No
- ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - Yes
- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

Notes: As far as we know, no specific taboos regarding food, clothing, and space exist in the church.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: In the infamous 2014 McDonald's homicide, a group of six was accused of murdering a businesswoman in a McDonald's restaurant in the eastern Chinese city of Zhaoyuan. According to their depositions at court, they recognized the woman to be an "evil spirit" (xieling 邪靈) that they felt the need to kill. The Chinese government quickly blamed the crime on the CAG, but a few details do not seem to match this interpretation. For instance, two members of this group, Lü Yingchun and Zhang Fan, were revered by the others as other incarnations of Almighty God. However, this belief is clearly at odds with the CAG, according to which there is only one Second Christ.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: The CAG's restrictive and conservative view of sexuality is similar to other Protestant Evangelical traditions.

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: As the CAG promotes a rigorously iconoclastic and ritual-critic position, its writings clearly oppose any kind of "magic."

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: Besides regular church service and writing testimonies, spreading the faith is among the most crucial duties for practitioners.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: In the case of the CAG, devotional adherence (faith) is more important than ritual correctness.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Many writings and testimonies attest to the widespread belief that nonbelievers (i.e., members of rivalrous Christian communities who fail to accept the CAG's supremacy) will be punished by Almighty God. For instance, CAG practitioners circulated a book called "Typical Cases of Leaders in Catholicism and Christianity in Mainland China Who Resist Almighty God Being Punished," which depicts the fate of those who fail to accept the church's teachings.

Reference: Dunn, Emily. *Lightning from the East: Heterodoxy and Christianity in Contemporary China*. Leiden: Brill, 2015.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: Unlike many other Christian traditions, the CAG does not place much emphasis on the concepts of heaven and hell. Instead, the focal point of attention is the advent of the future age of the Millennial Kingdom (qiannian guodu 千年國度) during which Satan will be bound and the wicked ones have been punished.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Punishments related to nonbelief and failing to accept Almighty God's teachings are significant in the church.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– I don't know

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The anthology "Didang Quannengshen zao chengfa de dianxing shili (wanli zhong jin xuan 877 li) 抵擋全能神遭懲罰的典型事例 (萬例中僅選877例)" (Typical Cases of Punishment for Resisting Almighty God. 877 Cases Selected from Ten Thousand Ones) provides many cases in which nonbelievers who clearly rejected and defamed the CAG were killed by Almighty God.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - No
 - Notes: Concerns about fertility and childbearing are entirely absent from CAG's scriptures.
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

Notes: Practitioners believe Christ's second advent has already appeared, and he was incarnated as a woman in the early 1990s. Her speeches were collected and published as the CAG's focal scripture *Hua zai roushen xianxian* 話在肉身顯現 (The Word Appears in the Flesh) in two volumes. While CAG material is unanimously silent about her identity, in 2012, Chinese authorities revealed Yang Xiangbin 楊向彬 (b. 1973) from Shaanxi Province as her true identity. However, this claim has not been corroborated by CAG or external observers and scholars. According to Emily Dunn's research, since ca. 2017, CAG material replaced speaking about the female Christ with male pronouns for unknown reasons.

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– No

Notes: The Second Christ has already arrived.

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Coming has already passed:

– Yes

Notes: The advent of the Second Christ appeared in ca. 1991.

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

Notes: Even though the CAG does not promote any specific political system, its writings abhor the Chinese Communist Party (CCP) because it is recognized as the "Great Red Dragon" (dahonglong 大紅龍), which, in turn, is a well-known incarnation of Satan in Revelation 12. Accordingly, the CAG's claim that Almighty God will eventually defeat the Great Red Dragon implies a rupture regarding China's political system. Yet, the church's writings do not explicitly describe how this will look like.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: The Second Christ will bring about the third and final period of the Millennial Kingdom (qiannian guodu 千年國度), which is loosely modeled after the descriptions in Revelation. In this period, Satan (i.e., the Anti-Christ and the Great Red Dragon, which CAG practitioners identify as the Chinese Communist Party) will be defeated by Almighty God.

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: The time of the advent of the Millennial Kingdom is not precisely known, but the Second Christ's activities and teachings are to bring it about.

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– Yes

Notes: They are required to spread the CAG's Gospel.

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

Notes: Even though the CAG does not promote any specific political system, it abhors the Chinese Communist Party (CCP) because it is recognized as the "Great Red Dragon" (dahonglong 大紅龍) of Revelation 12 (i.e., Satan). Accordingly, the CAG's claim that Almighty God will eventually defeat the Great Red Dragon implies a rupture regarding China's political system.

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: Nonbelievers and those who have slandered and defamed Almighty God will be severely punished (most often, killed).

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– No

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– No

↳ Generosity / charity:

– No

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Notes: Devout practitioners must avoid traditional Chinese beliefs and practices, including visiting temples and praying to deities.

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– No

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

Notes: Despite the CAG's strong opposition to the Chinese Communist Party (which they view as the Great Red Dragon depicted in Revelation 12), its social values have been profoundly influenced by experiences of the Maoist era. Accordingly, loyalty and strict obedience to Almighty God resemble the values cherished in the mass campaigns during that period. Because many leaders and practitioners are middle-aged or older, they must have witnessed the Maoist campaigns very well. Hence, most of them are familiar with these values.

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– No

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

Notes: In accordance with standard Christian fashion, CAG texts emphasize that practitioners have to undergo tribulations and "tests" (shilian 試煉) to refine their faith. The terms used, such as shilian, are also standardly used in other Christian contexts and in the Bible.

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - No
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - No
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
 - Notes: It is crucial to be grateful for Almighty God's mercy.
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - No
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - No
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - No
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory

painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Even though there is next to no fieldwork data available, evidence from CAG handbooks suggests that practitioners are expected to meet three times per week for two hours at a time to listen to sermons and discuss them afterward.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: The Church of Almighty God clearly distinguishes between in-group and out-group.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:
I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: Coreligionists are usually addressed as brothers and sisters.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Even though there is little information available, CAG seems to levy tithes.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

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